

Інновації в оптимізації бізнес-процесів

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Анотація. У статті висвітлюється сутність аутсорсингу, зокрема ІТ-аутсорсингу. Аутсорсинг в ІТ-сервісах (ІТ аутсорсинг, аутсорсинг інформаційних систем, інформаційних технологій) визначається як надання комплексних рішень для електронного бізнесу за допомогою зовнішніх експертів. ІТ-аутсорсинг також можна розуміти як прийняття сторонньою фірмою конкретних галузей бізнесу, пов'язаних з інформаційними технологіями (всі або тільки вибрані райони). Інвестиції в інформаційні технології та операційні витрати, пов'язані з операційною інфраструктурою, часто становлять значну частину бюджету. Описано та описано форми та види ІТ-аутсорсингу. Сутністю аутсорсингу, крім зниження витрат, є підтримка безперервного бізнес-процесу. Вважається, що для забезпечення належного функціонування, послуга компанії, яка спеціалізується на цій роботі, гарантовано буде краще виконана, ніж та, що виконується замовником. Компанія з аутсорсингу несе відповідальність за певні процедури, і, перш за все, ефективно усунення несправностей. Проаналізовано основні переваги та недоліки ІТ-аутсорсингу. Аутсорсинг став звичайною практикою в Західній Європі, Сполучених Штатах. Його роль в Україні зростає. Інформаційні системи часто є важливою сферою діяльності для різних компаній, які визнають переваги його використання. В умовах динамічно змінюваного середовища підприємства повинні мати ефективну та надійну систему, засновану на новітніх технологіях. Рішення про впровадження ІТ-аутсорсингу може стати чудовою можливістю для підвищення конкурентних переваг та можливості підвищення ефективності.

Ключові слова: аутсорсинг, підприємство, ІТ-аутсорсинг, ІТ-послуги, бізнес-процеси.

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Innovations in streamlining of business processes

Annotation. The article outlines the essence of outsourcing, and specifically IT outsourcing. Outsourcing in IT services (IT outsourcing, outsourcing of information systems, information technology) is defined as providing comprehensive solutions for e-business with the help of external experts. IT outsourcing can also be understood as the acceptance by the outside firm of specific areas of business related to information technology (all or only selected areas). Investments in information technology and operating costs related to operational infrastructure often make up a significant part of the budget. Forms and types of IT outsourcing are described and described. The essence of outsourcing, in addition to reducing costs, is the support of a continuous business process. It is believed that in order to ensure the proper functioning of the service, the company specializing in this work is guaranteed to be better performed than that performed by the customer. Outsourcing company is responsible for certain response procedures, and above all, for effective troubleshooting. The main advantages and disadvantages of IT outsourcing are analyzed. Outsourcing has become a common practice in Western Europe, the United States. His role in Ukraine is increasing. Information systems are often a distinguished area of activity for various companies that recognize the benefits of its use. Because in a dynamically changing environment, you need to have an efficient and reliable system based on the latest technology. The decision to introduce IT outsourcing can be a great opportunity to increase the competitive advantage and the opportunity to increase its efficiency.

Keywords: outsourcing, enterprise, IT outsourcing, IT services, business processes.

Introduction

Outsourcing is a management method, which in recent years has gained popularity in business. Outsourcing is playing an increasingly important role in the effective management of the company. Successfully using outsourcing information technology (IT). Among the reasons for outsourcing in this area, one can mention the opportunity to access the latest information technology, the ability to use the services of professionals with a great deal of experience and knowledge, the desire to focus managers on the strategy and focus on the core business. In addition, outsourcing services are cheaper because the specialized company is better able to use human resources and infrastructure, and the cost is distributed to more people. Specialization is also a factor in improving the quality of service and is associated with an emphasis on investment development in this area.

The problem of developing and implementing IT outsourcing to the economy was researched by many foreign and domestic scientists, in particular Aubert B., Rivard S., Patry M [3], Grover V., Cheon M. J., Teng J. [10], Kocpczyński T. [17] and others, but beyond the attention of scientists there are still many aspects.

The purpose of this article is to determine the nature and types of IT outsourcing, emphasize the benefits of its use and signal its presence in the Polish market.

Results

New information technologies have appeared and spread in the 80's and 90's and early twenty-first century as a result of the information revolution. Since the early 80's there was a rapid development of applications for personal computers, which caused a revolution in information systems of all organizations and individuals. In the economy, public administration, public services (education, health care), household (work), entertainment,

computer science and individual users - as a rule, began to use personal computers and their networks (local). It was also noted that a well-organized and efficient enterprise management system would help defeat competitors in order to reduce their risk and win the trust of their customers. In the early 1990s, a worldwide network of millions of computers and integration of the Internet (Internet) network was created.

In the modern world, the role of the Internet is undoubtedly essential, and the availability of the Internet becomes a necessity [1]. This is not only a source of diverse information, but also the cheapest means of communication. Thus, this tool is increasingly used by modern enterprises. A global computer network provides organizations that do not exist until now, development opportunities. More often and more often, we use the notion of a "new economy" in the context of the use of the Internet and information technology. New economic reality driven by entirely new technologies helps to stay in close cooperation and interpenetrating relationships. The new economy has a digital character [2].

The technologies of internal communications inside the organization, called Intranet (internal information network), are developed. Internet and intranet services based on telecommunication schemes, which are constantly expanding and developing due to new applications. An important component of new information technology near computers, data banks, are peripherals, communication networks, data networks, cellular telephony. New information technologies are also developing so-called media sectors, that is television, radio, cinema, video, which form the basis for their integration [11]. Internet and other modern information technologies create new business opportunities, both in terms of operational management (marketing, financial management, logistics management, production, human resources) and strategic management. Its use leads to significant changes in the methods and structures of management. Changes in management caused by new information technologies on the life cycle curve are at the beginning of the growth phase.

Due to the dynamic development of information technology, we can provide a full range of services. Colocation (infrastructure memory access) refers to the management of the computer environment, at all levels of its life, from the process of purchasing infrastructure by installing new equipment, distributing software systems, upgrading, maintaining and replacing old equipment. Managing desktop computers, laptops, servers, printers, scanners, file servers (FTPs), print servers [12] is stuck on computers.

Information systems are currently working to manage both small businesses and large enterprises. There is a tendency to refuse to control the internal work of the system. Increasingly, these services are provided outside of the specialized service companies that are the subject of outsourcing. Information technology has become an important direction for the company, which has found a specific reflection in outsourcing. Following was the transfer of entire departments of information to third parties. This was due not only to the desire to reduce costs, but also the need to keep pace with the rapidly evolving technology [13].

Outsourcing in IT services (IT outsourcing, outsourcing of information systems, information technology) is defined as providing comprehensive solutions for e-business with the help of external experts [1].

IT outsourcing can also be understood as the acceptance by the outside firm of specific areas of business related to information technology (all or only selected areas). Investments in information technology and operating costs related to operational infrastructure often make up a significant part of the budget. Applied information technologies for a long time affect the level and quality of business processes. The company should select its intended information technology according to clearly defined priorities and based on thorough feasibility studies. A well-developed IT strategy ensures the proper functioning of the outsourcing model [14]. Outsourcing is part of the company's strategic plan, it has a long-term character, and the service provider is a partner, not a supplier.

IT outsourcing is also defined as a process adopted by an organization aimed at signing an outsourcing agreement and upgrading IT assets, using collaboration with other recipients. As part of the services and information services, they relate to the work of introducing hardware and software in order to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of activities [2].

IT outsourcing is that the organization transfers only some (partial outsourcing) or almost all functions (outsourcing comprehensive / complete) to the executor, but leaving its own function of employee control and control of the entire project. IT outsourcing has, basically, the nature of the outsourcing contract, for which the company can not afford a function in the field of information systems and their implementation becomes an independent economic entity on the basis of the contract. Outsourcing involves the transfer of an external company responsible for maintaining the information system of work (or part thereof) in exchange for remuneration [3].

The smooth boundary between simple services such as maintenance of equipment produced over a long period of time in the context of the after-sales guarantee and actual outsourcing, where the company passes to a specialist a wide range of activities that can not carry out their professional staff. According to E Banachovich, the difference between outsourcing and the usual transfer of work primarily is that outsourcing leads to a remodeling of the system around the core business and the construction of long-term relationships with the service provider [15]. In the case of IT outsourcing, the role of the manager and the IT department changes - and so the contractor becomes a customer. Existing employees, if they stay in organizations, become experts in learning the needs of users and their service providers [4].

The essence of outsourcing, in addition to reducing costs, is the support of a continuous business process. It is believed that in order to ensure the proper functioning of the service, the company specializing in this work is guaranteed to be better performed than that performed by the customer. Outsourcing company is responsible for certain response procedures, and above all, for effective troubleshooting. Thus, outsourcing saves about 40% of the amount spent in the initial period. The ultimate advantage is the effect of a financial leverage achieved through savings, which in the original model - the amount of lost profits [5].

You can distinguish the following types of IT outsourcing [6]:

- according to goals:

o Tactical - an unstable relationship that is not related to the development of the strategic goals of the parent company, ie is implemented for a period shorter than the horizon of the strategic development of the parent company, seeking to achieve a specific goal, for example: reducing costs by reducing jobs in the region information technology team.

o Strategic - the long-term relationship associated with the strategy of the parent company's development in the strategic horizons, the strategic approach to corporate information issues stems from the idea of business of the company.

- according to the range:

o Full - Moving the whole IT infrastructure to a third party. In this case, always part of the employees of the customer companies is displayed to the main means of the artist,

o selective - external management of the company in selected areas (management of a selected network of applications, Internet infrastructure)

- by type:

o the sharing of computing power - the outsourcer (the person responsible for the outsourcing process) does not enter into information - what programs are executed on the equipment of the client,

o Application maintenance - infrastructure maintenance and maintenance and IT support for data applications,

o business processes - the division of entire business processes and the trust of their outsourcing company, for example, installation and maintenance of information systems at the enterprise ..

- by location [16]:

o central services - Data Center - managed by the outsourcing company's center;

o local services - managed by the client.

In the literature, there are different ways to classify outsourcing IT services. B Ober, S. Rivard and M. Party define it as a recipe for external companies in the system of service tasks, and K.P. Arnett and M.C. Jones applied a more detailed classification, including system integration, object management, contract programming, software support, network maintenance, while maintaining the main computer and workstations. V. Grover, M.J. Cheon and J. Teng are referred to as IT outsourcing development of applications and services, system operations, networks (telecommunications management), as well as IT support, planning and management systems, and the acquisition of application software [7].

According to a study by IBM Global Services, the most important benefits of IT outsourcing [8]:

1. Access to world-class technologies.

2. Accelerating the benefits of restructuring (reengineering).

3. It is better to concentrate the company on its main tasks.

4. Stability and predictability of maintenance costs for IT systems.

5. Protection against dismissal from the work of informatics.

6. Guarantee of integrated service system.

7. Guarantee of continuity of work of information systems.

8. Appropriate adjustment of computer science to business needs.

9. Guarantee the creation of a professional strategy for IT development, in accordance with business needs [17].

According to G. Hodak's research, the most important reasons for using IT outsourcing are: cost reduction (68%), lack of experience in IT (60%), desire to focus on core business (45%), systemic failure reduction (38%) access to new technologies (26%), search for competitive advantages (23%), difficulties in keeping IT staff (19%) and protection against dismissal from computer science (9%) [9].

IT outsourcing provides a constant level of spending for several years. Its advantage is relatively inexpensive access to the latest technology. Companies that specialize in such activities are much easier to take on the costs of upgrading and updating application hardware. In addition, if necessary, it can use additional resources very quickly - permanently or temporarily. Most importantly, the client is responsible for obtaining a high-class specialist, and their salaries are distributed among several individuals [10].

The company decides to use IT outsourcing to get rid of all the shortcomings (variety of systems, duplication of work, risk of errors leading to delays and losses). The best solution for an enterprise is the availability of IT that allows you to connect areas related to enterprise management, so that one place can be processed and archived data. IT solutions cover only individual areas of management. The emergence of many areas of data must be replaced between the departments of the company and may be the source of errors, especially manual transmission of data between systems [18].

One can conclude that the Polish IT outsourcing market is still ripe. Organizations understood the concept of isolating certain areas of activity and the need for cooperation with an external source in order to achieve mutual benefit. The experience of recent years concludes that The Polish IT outsourcing market is different from the Western market, which is manifested primarily in price relations. [19] American and Western European customers, by signing a contract, enter into a relationship with the company that costs it, such as them, or

lower, moving service centers in countries such as Mexico, Poland, Russia, India and China. Outsourcing companies tend to standardize contracts and services, which in turn allows them to reduce costs. One can also say that many cases of successful contracts are realized not only by large suppliers, but also by smaller companies that are approaching the customer's needs.

Conclusions

Outsourcing has become a common practice in Western Europe, the United States. His role in Ukraine is increasing. Information systems are often a distinguished area of activity for various companies that recognize the benefits of its use. Because in a dynamically changing environment, you need to have an efficient and reliable system based on the latest technology [20]. The decision to introduce IT outsourcing can be a great opportunity to increase the competitive advantage and the opportunity to increase its efficiency. Thus, we see that the field of IT outsourcing in Ukraine will be steadily growing. Polish companies that want to implement this type of outsourcing can benefit from the wide experience of foreign organizations that are successful in this field. This is due to the ability to avoid many dangers and *can be a perspective for further research*.

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